

Abstract**ETYMOLOGICAL FEATURES OF ZOONOMIC
PHRASEOLOGISMS IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE****Ochildiyeva Zuhra Kholnazarovna**

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This article reveals the etymological features of zoonomic phraseological units. To determine the specific characteristics of the zoonomic cultural code in the French language, phraseological units with animal components are of particular interest. While animals acquire symbolic meanings, they serve as corresponding linguistic markers of certain human qualities, reflecting the experiences of speakers of this language.

Current time in linguistics zoonyms lexical - semantic features to study various in directions take is going on . In this mainly , animal of names semantic to the structure separately attention is given . French in the language zoonomic cultural code to oneself typical features determination for animal structural to the part has was phraseological units separately interest wakes up . Man external appearance essentially social to the character has . In it all psychic features and to them typical creative activity development The sources are , of course , all around . social in the environment , that is in society own on the contrary finds . Man external appearance realistic existence with related in a way his/her social marriage through to the eye is thrown away . Here this in the sense human external of the image appearance people with each other in a relationship to the surface coming social experience possession from the process It consists of . as a result human psychic characteristics , morals qualities , character , willpower qualities , interests , beliefs and worldview content finds .

Human external appearance to describe and him/her in the language reflection to hold for and phraseological of units contribution much is significant . meaning formation to oneself typical complicated is a process . Meaning in the formation in reality of the object important characteristic - signs reflection to find simple process not , maybe this features human social activity , experience point from the point of view important maybe necessary . Again more precisely as in other words , like this importance ownership social experience based on to the surface comes . Psycholinguists meaning " human being " of activity appearance changed " shape " error in definition they didn't do it , because perception being done of the object features human social activity in the process to the eye will be thrown away and [Sh . Safarov :175.] . This instead , French of the language zoomorphic code French language and culture owners worldview to oneself typical features open giver interesting event that emphasize to the goal according to . This code universal to be regardless national to oneself originality with separated In particular , animals symbolic meaning profession reached without this in the language speakers experience reflection provider known one human of virtues suitable linguistic from the signs one is considered .

My name is component French phraseological of units most human character expression . Phraseological units with a zoonomic component (*hereinafter referred to as ZKFB*) are represented by various structural models. For example, they include the component parts of

the names of animals, birds, fish, insects and reptiles and serve to reflect the features characteristic of humans. The figurative nature of phraseological units is revealed by interlinking their literal meaning. This phenomenon indicates that speakers perceive the concept based on a phraseological unit differently, depending on their intellectual and general education level, as well as individual characteristics [Yu.G. Sinelnikov, SA Androsova: 50]. In studying the system of linguistic signs, it is important to identify stereotypes and norms of national culture, to understand the specific features of perception of the world. Because, "comparing its specific features with "inhuman" features is perceived as "norms of human features"" [V.N. Teliya: 241].

Also, studies have shown that a large number of French phraseological units with a zoonym component affect various aspects of human appearance and are generally universal. Phraseologisms with a zoonym component such as " *whale*", " *cow*", " *pig*", " *quail*", " *cat*", " *dog*", " *tick* " are used to denote physical characteristics of a person. The components " *rat*", " *crab*", " *goat*", " *pig* " act as symbols of various facial features of a person. The characteristic "clothes and cleanliness" is considered from the point of view of the neatness or filthiness of a person's appearance. In this case, zoonyms such as " *rabbit*", " *monkey*", " *bear*", " *louse*", " *pig*", " *crow*", " *duck* " are characterized. " *Worm* " is used to describe behavior. Zoonyms " *zebra*", " *elephant*", " *frog*", " *crow*", " *pig*", " *duck*", " *turtle*", " *snake* " denote different types of gait. French phraseological units with components " *dog*", " *monkey*", " *goat*", " *frog*", " *lice* " characterize varying degrees of attractiveness of a person. It should be noted that a large number of French phraseological units with zoonymic components have a negative evaluative character. Animal species such as " *goat*", " *pig*", " *dog*", " *rat*", " *crab*", " *frog*", " *lice*", " *crow*", " *duck* " and " *monkey* " can be the embodiment of a number of properties. Undoubtedly, the images inherent in each animal in the linguistic consciousness of speakers play an important role in the selection of a particular zoomorphic component in phraseological units.

Body condition . To express the fullness of a person, that is, obesity, " *whale*", " *cow*", " *pig* " and Animal names such as " *quail* " are used: " *gros comme une baleine* " ("fat as a whale") " *gras comme un cochon* " ("fat as a pig") - "very fat". The zoonyms " *cat* " and " *dog* " are widely used to describe thinness: " *maigre comme un chat de gouttière* " - (thin as a house cat), " *maigre comme un chien fou* ("thin as a mad dog") - "very thin, skinny as a stick". In French phraseological units, *tique* is used to express characteristics characteristic of a short person. The word (kana) is used: " *ne pas être plus grand qu'un tique* ". For example, in literary texts they also have this meaning:

" *Mais, sur mon honneur, le voilà devenu aussi gras qu'un cochon* " (De Las Cases E. Mémorial de Sainte-Hélène. 1963. p. 321). / *Honestly, he's fat as a pig*. (Translation by the authors)

Facial features . Through the results of the analysis, it was determined that the following zoonyms are means of describing a person's appearance:

- Animal names such as *le rat* (rat) and *le crabe* (crab) are symbols of an ugly face: " *avoir la face de rat* " (to have a rat face).
- The components " *rat* " and " *goat* " are used to express the negative nature of a person's gaze: " *avaler un rat* " (to look displeased), " *avoir les yeux de chèvre morte* " ("to have the eyes of a dead goat") - "to have an embarrassed look."
- Phraseological units with the component " *frog* " give a positive assessment of a person's gaze: " *faire un œil de crapaud mort d'amour* " (literal translation: "to look with the eyes of a frog dying of love") - to look with eyes full of love.

- *Cochon* (pig) refers to the small and tiny size of the eyes: "*avoir l'œil de cochon*" – "to have small and deep-set eyes"

Describing clothes . It is worth noting that the word *le lapin* (rabbit) refers to the neat appearance of the clothes worn by a person: "*être propre comme un lapin*" (to be very neat). Analysis has shown that animals such as "*monkey*", "*bear*", "*lice*", "*pig*", "*crow*" and "*duck*" describe carelessly chosen clothes, disorder and used to express distaste. For example:

"*to have the appearance of a monkey in boots*" (to be ugly/look like a monkey);

"*to be dirty like a lice* (to be infested with lice);

"*aller comme un pardessus à un canard*" (to walk with a dirty head).

Such phraseology is also often found in literary texts: *J'en viens à toi, Moulu. Tu es un nid à poux, ça ne peut pas durer ... tu es sale comme un cochon!*" (Sartre J.-P. *La Mort dans l'âme*. Livre de poche, 1962. p. 64]. / *I came for you, Moulu. You are a scumbag, this cannot go on like this... you are as dirty as a pig*. (Authors' translation)

Walking. The phraseological unit *le zèbre* (zebra) is used to describe a person who always walks quickly, as if in a hurry: "*courir comme un zèbre*" (to run like a zebra). Animal names such as "*elephant*", "*frog*", "*crow*", "*pig*" and "*duck*" are used to describe a clumsy gait:

"*être comme un éléphant dans un magasin de porcelaine(s)*" – to be careless;

"*se dandiner comme un canard*" - quack like a duck;

la tortue (turtle) refer to a person's slow walking: "*aller comme une tortue*" - to walk like a turtle.

le serpent (snake) is used to describe crawling :

- "*(se) glisser comme un serpent (or une couleuvre)*" - (to crawl like a snake).

le crabe (crab) are used to describe a person's gait, meaning a waddling gait:

- "*marcher en crabe*" - to walk with a limp.

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